

Synthesis and *in vitro* electrochemical study of composite coatings on implant by electrophoretic deposition

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Abstract : The aim of the present study is the preparation and characterization of silicon dioxide, zinc oxide and its composite. The above inorganic biomaterials were synthesized by sol-gel method. The nosocomial infections or a hospital-acquired infection of an implant (biofilm) dramatically increases the risk of orthopaedic implant surgery. The biofilm infections of an implant or prostheses can be preventable with better surface modification of bioactive and corrosion resistance composite coatings of 70% SiO₂ with 30% ZnO by electrophoretic deposition (EPD). The prepared powders and its coatings were characterized by Powder X-ray diffraction, *in vitro* electrochemical studies such as Tafel polarization and electrochemical impedance analyses.

Keywords : Ti-6Al-4V implant alloy, corrosion study, electrophoretic deposition, impedance analysis.

Introduction

Silicon dioxide, zinc oxide has been synthesized by sol-gel method that has found to be of nanosized particles with various applications of pharmaceutical and its allied sector like biomedical¹. The bioactive nature, high heat and chemical resistance of silica could be used for corrosion resistance and formation of osseointegration for bioinert biomaterials such as metals². Zinc oxide of nanostructures has been found uses in exploratory and biomedical applications with antiseptic antibacterial activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria; in addition to that its film improves the lubricity and wear resistance of implanted biomaterials^{3,4}. The increase in longevity and life expectancy of mankind, the debilitating diseases of bones and joints associated with elderly people found to be increased. Hence improved biomaterials and the processing techniques for implants and prostheses have to be developed those that have been used in orthopaedic, dental, ophthalmological, cardiovascular, cochlear and maxillofacial applications⁵.

The failure of implants is due to the chronic inflammation, debris formation (wearing or cracking), friction,

stress shielding, leaching out of ions around the implant during implantation surgery. The infected implant should be treated with medications possibly may not work due to the presence of the impervious fibrous layer^{6,7}. However with better knowledge of the interactions between the micro-organism, the implant and the host, researchers are finding ways to improve qualities of individual biomaterials by the way of nanotechnologies, inorganic-organic hybrid technologies and composites, to make a better prosthetic device in order to avoid a devastating complications such as high morbidity and mortality, increased antibiotics use, prolonged hospital stay, repeated debridement and prolonged rehabilitations⁸. Several standard surgical implant materials such as stainless steel, Co-Cr based alloys, titanium and its alloys are used in orthopaedic and dental prostheses as biomaterials. Among these Ti-6Al-4V is used as an implant material for biomedical and dental applications due to its owing most of the better properties of biomaterials. Nanostructure materials and coatings are produced by various methods such as conventional, sol-gel, PVD and CVD, etc., alternatively electrophoretic deposition (EPD) could be an at-

tracting biomaterial coating technique because of its high purity on deposits, the wide range of coating thickness with the cost-effective applicability to large and complex shaped implants and prostheses. The application of composite coating with ZnO over implant is the better way to minimize the failure of the implant due to bacterial infection. Hence, an effort has been made to overcome the corrosion resistance and cracking of the coating during implantation.

In this present work, efforts has been taken to synthesis the nanosized SiO₂, ZnO and its composite materials for electrophoretic deposition on Ti-6Al-4V alloy as well as characterization by powder XRD, *in vitro* electrochemical studies such as Tafel polarization and EIS analyses.

Experimental

Preparation of SiO₂ :

SiO₂ nanoparticles were prepared by using tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) 98% purity as silica precursor, was dissolved in DD water with stirring. The resultant content was transferred into R.B. flask fitted with condenser and conc. nitric acid was used to maintain the pH of the solution under vigorous stirring. After that the mixture was aged in an oil bath at 90 °C for 3 h. The formed gel was transferred to Petri dish and allowed to dry in the oven for 36 h and finally sintered at 600 °C for 2 h. The heating rate was 1 °C/min and allowed to cool the sintered sample for one day. Identification of phase was done by using powder XRD.

Preparation of ZnO :

A homogeneous solution of DD water, triethanolamine and ethanol were prepared in a container. This solution was transferred to the vessel containing 0.5 M zinc nitrate hexahydrate with continuous stirring. After addition, the resultant solution pH was adjusted by using ammonium hydroxide. The precipitate was then washed with DD water by three-four times and filtered through Whatmann filter paper. The residue was dried in an oven at 100 °C for 2 h and sintered at 900 °C for 2 h.

Electrophoretic deposition :

The Ti-6Al-4V substrate was polished using 220 to

1200 grits emery paper followed by diamond paste then washed with DD water and ultrasonic clean in acetone for 20 min. The suspension for coating was prepared by taking (70%) of SiO₂ and (30%) of ZnO in 75 ml isopropyl alcohol and 1 ml of *n*-butyl amine, 100 mg of PVP, 100 mg of ethyl cellulose was added as additives and allowed to stand overnight. The Ti-6Al-4V alloy (anode) and 316 LSS (cathode) electrode were fixed at 1 cm apart and were used as working and counter electrodes respectively. The coatings were deposited at the voltage of 95 V with various time of 1 min to 5 min. The optimized coated samples were dried at room temperature and then sintered at 300 °C for 30 min.

Characterization techniques :

The XRD patterns were recorded in an X-ray diffractometer (D8 model, BRUKER, Germany) with a step size of 0.02° and a scan rate of 1°/min with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$). For electrochemical analysis, a cell volume of 500 ml Ringer's biological solution was used at a pH of 7.4 by using Ti-6Al-4V alloy, platinum and Ag/AgCl (S.C.E.) as working, auxiliary and reference electrodes respectively. From the polarization curve, the E_{corr} , I_{corr} values of uncoated and coated substrate was determined by Tafel extrapolation method. EIS measurements were carried out using (Gill AC Potentiostat/galvanostat frequency response analyzer, UK). The measurements of the EIS were performed at OCP using a frequency scan from 10000 Hz to 0.1 Hz. Both Nyquist and Bode plots were analyzed by software analyzer to determine the parameters such as charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) and double layer capacitance (C_{dl}).

Results and discussion

XRD analysis :

Fig. 1 shows the combined XRD patterns of the silica, zinc oxide and its composite. Sintered silica has not revealed any well-defined homogeneous crystalline phase but an amorphous hump appeared in-between 20–30 regions in the sintered sample were attributed to hydrated silica. The sintered ZnO sample showed only pure ZnO phase, which was confirmed by the high diffraction peak at $2\theta = 36^\circ$. In the case of composite, the characteristic

Fig. 1. XRD of sintered silica, zinc oxide and its composite.

peak of silica hump decreased as intensity due to the amorphous nature of silica with limited crystallinity or the heavier zinc oxide particles well coated or adhered on silica by the mechanism of core-shell structure, hence ZnO peaks were predominant.

EIS and Tafel analyses :

Fig. 2 shows the potentiodynamic polarization curves of blank and various coated samples. The I_{corr} of com-

Fig. 2. Potentiodynamic polarization curves of blank, silica, ZnO and its composite on Ti-6Al-4V.

posite coating has lowest current density of 0.001234 mA/cm^2 , compared with blank, SiO_2 and ZnO coated implant such as 0.011248 mA/cm^2 , 0.003158 mA/cm^2 , and 0.003387 mA/cm^2 respectively. From these values the corrosion resistance of composite coating increases by many fold compared to blank and other coatings. Hence, with increase in E_{corr} with the decrease in I_{corr} value of the composite coatings suggests that better corrosion performance than the uncoated substrate. Fig. 3 shows the Nyquist study of uncoated and coated samples. The C_{dl} value of the uncoated alloy was found to be decreased from 1.458×10^{-4} to 4.891×10^{-5} Farads after the composite coating, which evidences the better corrosion resistance

Fig. 3. Nyquist plot of blank, silica, ZnO and composite on Ti-6Al-4V.

behavior. The R_{ct} value of zinc oxide, silica, composite coatings was found to be increased compared to blank (Table 1). From these results, it was confirmed that with the increased R_{ct} value of composite coating with the decrease in the C_{dl} value undoubtedly reveals the usage of coating for long term applications. The results are further substantiated with the protective nature of the coating with the increase in inhibition efficiency. The IE of 89.02% for the composite coating, 71.91% for SiO_2 and 73.24% for ZnO compared to blank substrates shows the capacity of corrosion resistance behaviors in human body environment. Both silica and zinc oxide more or less shows

Table 1. Potentiodynamic, EIS data of blank, ZnO, SiO_2 and its composite

Sample	E_{corr} (mV)	I_{corr} (mA/cm ²)	Corrosion rate (mpy)	IE (%)	R_{ct} (Ohms)	C_{dl} (Farads)
Blank	-338	0.011248	7.2314	-	9.073×10^2	1.458×10^{-4}
Zinc oxide	-241	0.003387	1.9346	73.24	9.945×10^2	5.593×10^{-4}
Silica	-237	0.003158	2.0307	71.91	1.570×10^3	2.226×10^{-5}
Composite	-153	0.001234	0.7938	89.02	3.3734×10^3	4.891×10^{-5}

the same IE when compared with blank. But composite having silica and zinc oxide has been showing a maximum IE of 89.02%, which is due to inhibitive effect of both SiO₂ and ZnO.

Conclusion

(i) SiO₂, ZnO powders were synthesized by sol-gel technique by using precursors such as TEOS and zinc nitrate hexahydrate and the formation of phase was confirmed by powder XRD.

(ii) The composite having 70% of SiO₂ and 30% of ZnO was prepared and successfully deposited on Ti-6Al-4V by EPD method.

(iii) The Ti-6Al-4V alloy with composite coating exhibited a good passive behavior in Ringer's solution by electrochemical techniques such as potentiodynamic polarization (Tafel) and Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS). The results from Tafel analysis were consistent with that Nyquist analysis for the composite coatings.

(iv) Thus, with the positive shift in the nobler direction for the composite coating from the Tafel polarization and the shift in the high frequency time constant from the bode plot having approximately 10⁴ also corroborates its better resistive behavior.

Hence from the above analytical study, we conclude that synthesis of pure silicon dioxide, zinc oxide and its

composite are possible, as well as efficient surface modification of an implant achieved by electrophoretic deposition method for producing better biomaterial activity of biocompatibility to human body environment for better osseous with possible avoidance of microbial contamination of an implant.

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